

New floristic records from Central Europe 17 (reports 252-263)

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Abstract: The presented 17th part of the series includes twelve new records of vascular plants from the countries of Central Europe. New records of three alien taxa are reported for Czechia, *Sorbus hybrida*, *Styphnolobium japonicum* and *Primula ×digenea*. Three new *Taraxacum* species belonging to section *Taraxacum*, *T. croceiflorum*, *T. lippertianum* and *T. expallidiforme* are reported for the first time from the territory of Slovakia. *Mahonia aquifolium* and *Viburnum lantana* are reported from Poland and *Catalpa ovata* and *Daphne laureola* from Hungary. Two new populations of the rare species *Veronica opaca* were found in southern and eastern Slovakia. A recent population of *Taraxacum parnassicum*, belonging to sect. *Erythroperma*, is reported for the flora of Romania supplemented by the results of a revision of herbarium specimens deposited in the public herbaria collections CL and PRA.

Keywords: adventive species, Czech Republic, chorology, Hungary, native species, new findings, Poland, red list species, Romania, Slovakia, *Taraxacum*, vascular plants.

This is an ongoing report in the established series dealing with new chorological data on higher vascular plants in Central Europe (for details, see *Thaiszia – J. Bot.* 28 (1), pp. 79–80, 2018).

The nomenclature of the taxa follows the Euro+Med PlantBase (Euro+Med 2006-) and/or Slovak and Czech versions of Pladias project (Chytrý et al. 2021; Kantor & Marhold 2024+), herbarium acronyms follow Thiers (2026+). Distribution data taken from the public database iNaturalist.org are cited as follows: iNaturalist ID and number of observation(s), with subsequent citation in the References.

The publication includes contributions by M. Dudáš (252), O. Obrtlík & L. Schwabová (253), G. Király & A. Theiler (254-255), A. Pliszko, A. Walczyk & K. Mroczkowski (256), A. Pliszko & G. Pacyna (257), B. Trávníček & M. Dudáš (258-260) and R. J. Vašut (261-263) arranged alphabetically.

Matej Dudáš (report 252)

Romania

252. *Taraxacum parnassicum* Dahlst.: Transylvania, Turda, Petreștii de Jos, Cheile Turzii, enter to the canyon from west, xerotherms grazed by sheep near parking place, frequent, 515 m, 46°34'15.42"N 23°40'2.74"E, 8. 5. 2025, M. Dudáš, KO 38429, BRNU 697629, rev. R. J. Vašut, iNaturalist ID 314546603, 314546617 and 314546611.

Specimens examined in the herbarium CL: Transsilvania, distr. Cluj. In graminosis supra vallem Plecica prope oppid. Cluj. Alt. cca 400 m s. m., leg. I. Prodan, Apr. 1923, CL 438176, Fl. Rom. Exs. (mixed specimen - only a single one plant is *T. parnassicum*, the other four plants belong to *T. sect. Taraxacum*). – Transsilvania. distr. Cojocna. In declivibus graminosis montis Hoia, prope oppid. Cluj. Alt. cca 480 m s. m., leg. E. J. Nyárády, 4. V. 1925, CL 429106 (tree plants are *T. parnassicum*). – Transsilvania. Distr. Turda. In “Cheia Turului” [=Cheile Turenilor], leg. Csűrös-Káptalan Margit, 2. V. 1957, CL 554712 (mixed specimen - only a single one plant is *T. parnassicum*, the other four plants belong to *T. sect. Erythrosperma*). – Transsilvania, distr. Alba. In graminosis montanis ad “Vapa Mică” prope pag. Colțești, leg. I. Gergely, 30. IV. 1956, CL 507782 (mixed specimen - only a single one plant is *T. parnassicum*).

Specimens examined in the herbarium PRA: Romania mer.-occid., regio Banat, pagus Girnic [= Gârnic]: in valle ad pagum, leg. J. Sádlo, IV.1987, PRA-00011523 – PRA-00011525, det. Kirschner & Štěpánek ut *T. silesiacum* (no. 7117), rev. M. Dudáš.

Taraxacum parnassicum, a triploid apomictic species belonging to *T.* sect. *Erythrosperma*, is a widely distributed species in major part of Europe. During the revision of herbarium material in public herbaria collections, several specimens collected in Romania were found. It occurs in dry and rocky xerothermic habitats in low grassy steppe vegetation, and it tolerates trampled surfaces and grazing by sheep. Overall, the diversity of *Taraxacum* in Romania has not been researched comprehensively yet and all recent data help to fill in the gap in this difficult genus. The species was not reported by Nyárády (1965), however, it is an autochthonous species in the flora of Romania.

Ondřej Obrtlík & Lenka Schwabová (report 253)

Slovakia

253. *Veronica opaca* Fr.: the Ipeľsko-rimavská brázda region, distr. Krupina, Hontianské Nemce (southernmost part of the village), roadside ditch on the W side of the road to Domaníky, near the car repair shop, ca 400 m SW of the railway station building, several dozens of individuals, 210 m, 48°16'39.2"N 18°59'21.1"E, 7779b, 14. 4. 2025, O. Obrtlík & L. Schwabová, OL 055688 (<https://ol.jacq.org/OL055688>), iNaturalist ID 270616022, 270395981, Fig. 1. – the Slanské vrchy Mts, Slanec, distr. Košice-okolie, yard covered with stone chippings in front of the house at 321/3 Forgáčova street, right next to a parking lot, ca twenty individuals, 370 m, 48°38'11.376"N, 21°28'28.399"E, 7394d, 12. 4. 2026, O. Obrtlík, L. Schwabová & L. Kobrlová, OL 055730 (<https://ol.jacq.org/OL055730>), iNaturalist IDs 349315275, 349291977.

Veronica opaca has always been regarded as extremely rare in Slovakia. In the latest version of the Slovak Red List, it is classified as critically endangered (Eliáš et al. 2015). In this report, we present two newly discovered localities of the species. During April 2025, *V. opaca* was documented in a roadside drainage ditch near the village of Hontianské Nemce. Surprisingly, the ditch supported several dozen flowering individuals. The second locality, situated within the built-up area of the village of Slanec, was found a year later. Around twenty specimens occurred in a front yard covered with quarry stone chippings. In both cases, the plants grew directly among bare stone debris, which is an atypical habitat for this species. *V. opaca* is a declining and rare arable weed, typically associated with root crop fields and vegetable gardens (Hügin & Hügin 1994; Peniašteková 1997; Hrouda 2000). Hrouda (2000) notes that the species tends to avoid other types of ruderal (synanthropic) habitats. Therefore, its occurrences in a roadside ditch and a built-up area are both unusual and noteworthy. Hügin & Hügin (1994) compared *V. opaca* with closely related *V. persica* and *V. polita*. In this comparison, *V. opaca* appears to be a specialist with distinct climatic, habitat and soil requirements and a relatively restricted distribution range. *V. opaca* is considered an indicator of light, skeletal, freshly moist, nutrient-rich soils with a slightly acidic to neutral reaction (Hügin & Hügin 1994; Peniašteková 1997; Hrouda 2000).

The newly discovered occurrence near Hontianské Nemce is located relatively close to the few previously known localities in the phytogeographic districts of Pohronský Inovec and Vtáčnik. By contrast, the locality in Slanec lies in eastern Slovakia, a region with only a single previous record of the species. In 1885, a herbarium specimen of *V. opaca* was collected by Veselény in the vicinity of Prešov (Peniašteková 1997). Our finding represents the first record from this area in more than 140 years. More recently, in 2022, the species was recorded during the SBS and ČBS floristic course held in Senica. An excursion group led by M. Valachovič documented it in fields near the village of Borský Mikuláš (Eliáš et al. 2025). Although three new localities have been recorded in recent years, these records most likely represent previously overlooked populations rather than the evidence of an ongoing expansion of the species in Slovakia.

Fig. 1 *Veronica opaca* at the newly discovered locality near Hontianské Nemce (Slovakia), growing in a roadside drainage ditch on skeletal, gravelly substrate. A) plant habit in situ, B) capsule and its indumentum. Photographed by L. Schwabová.

Gergely Király & Angéla Theiler (reports 254-255)

Hungary

254. *Daphne laureola* L.: Hungary, NW Hungary, Győr-Moson-Sopron County, Sopron, Bajcsy-Zs. Street, mature, fully grown specimen in an abandoned part of a school park, 225 m, 47°40'47.7"N 16°34'41.6"E, 8365b, 27. 11. 2025, G. Király, Fig. 2.

Spurge-laurel is an Atlantic–Mediterranean species that occurs in Hungary at the north-eastern edge of its range. In Hungary, it has significant populations in the Transdanubian Mountains (Keszthely Mts, Bakony, and Vértes). Additional occurrences in Transdanubia are either questionable or clearly of adventive origin (Keller 1999; Bartha et al. 2015; Barina & Csontos 2025). At the margins of the Carpathian Basin, the species is fairly common in Austria, particularly in the Northern Limestone Alps (reaching the eastern margins of the Vienna Woods and the Bucklige Welt), whereas in the Carpathians it occurs only in Romania (Meusel et al. 1978–1992; Fischer et al. 2008). In the region, the species is calciphilous, inhabiting beech, oak-hornbeam, Turkey and pubescent oak forests (Barina & Csontos 2025).

Data on naturalized occurrences have significantly increased over the past decades in Hungary, and in some places, these have resulted in the formation of stable subsynchronous populations (e.g. Lengyel 2005; Nagy & Exner 2014; Bauer 2022).

The newly discovered occurrence in Sopron (the first record for NW Hungary), although located barely 20 km in a straight line from the native populations in Austria, is certainly of a recent adventive origin. The site lies not far from the University Botanical Garden, where the species was planted from Hungarian wild populations, and where it has been spreading spontaneously for decades. Further local spread and long-term establishment in the humid deciduous forests of the Sopron Mts are highly likely, similarly to other already established evergreen species such as *Ilex aquifolium* and *Mahonia* spp.

255. *Catalpa ovata* G. Don: Kisalföld, Szigetköz region, Dunasziget, 1,5 km N of the “Denkpáli-hallépcső”, along the edge of a spontaneous willow stand, a mature individual, 115 m, 47°56'41.6"N 17°24'16.6"E, 8070c, 27. 06. 2025. G. Király, photodocumented.

An ornamental tree native to China (Knees 2000), with several records from Europe (Schmid 2005; Galasso et al. 2018; Pachschröll et al. 2024; Verloove 2026). In Hungary, it has been reported as a naturalized species in the vicinity of Pécs and Szekszárd, as well as in the Zemplén Mts (Wirth et al. 2020; Dudáš et al. 2021); in these cases, it was found in urbanized environments.

The character of the new occurrence in the Szigetköz (the first record for the Kisalföld macroregion) differs markedly from these earlier records. It was found at a considerable distance from settlements, near the Old Danube (Öreg-Duna) River. In this area, on higher-elevation parts of the floodplain and in pioneer secondary habitats, there is a realistic potential for long-term establishment and local spread.

Fig. 2 Spontaneously growing specimen of *Daphne laureola* in Sopron (Hungary). Photographed by G. Király.

Artur Pliszko, Agnieszka Walczyk & Kornel Mroczkowski (report 256)

Poland

256. *Mahonia aquifolium* (Pursh) Nutt.: southern Poland, Lesser Poland Province, Kraków, ruderal thickets in the former allotment gardens, 10 individuals, 197 m, 50°02.260'N 19°55.844'E, 16. 04. 2026, A. Pliszko, A. Walczyk & K. Mroczkowski.

Mahonia aquifolium (Pursh) Nutt (recently classified also as *Berberis aquifolium* Pursh, e.g. WFO: wfo-0000562782), a broadleaf evergreen shrub in the barberry family (Berberidaceae), is native to western North America, including Canada and the United States, from British Columbia to California (Whittemore 1997). It prefers open forests and shrublands but tolerates shade well (Whittemore 1997; Adriaens et al. 2019). It has been introduced as an ornamental and medicinal plant to other

parts of Canada and the United States, as well as to Europe, Asia, and Australia (Randall 2017; POWO 2026a). In Europe, it is established in many countries (von Raab-Straube 2015; Adriaens et al. 2019; Randall 2017) and is also considered invasive in Belgium (Adriaens et al. 2019) and Germany (Ross et al. 2009). The primary traits contributing to its invasiveness include rapid vegetative reproduction via root suckers and a high capacity for long-distance seed dispersal. This dispersal has been enhanced by the artificial selection of genes governing phenotypic traits, such as large inflorescences, which in turn leads to increased fruit and seed production (Ross et al. 2008; Adriaens et al. 2019).

In Poland, *B. aquifolium* is often cultivated as an ornamental plant in gardens and urban green spaces. Although its distribution throughout the country is poorly understood, established populations have been observed, for example, in Greater Poland (Purcel 2009) and Masovia (Szulc 2023). It is usually found in parks, cemeteries, hedges, and ruderal thickets, as well as in forests and on forest edges and roadsides (Purcel 2009; Danielewicz et al. 2020; Mirek et al. 2020; Czarna 2025). Moreover, it is treated as a potentially invasive alien species (Tokarska-Guzik et al. 2012).

We recorded a new site of *B. aquifolium* in Kraków, southern Poland, in April 2026. We found 10 individuals scattered in ruderal thickets in the former allotment gardens in Ludwinów, in the city's central-eastern part. The individuals were 18–90 cm tall and had 1–4 shoots, most of which were generative (Fig. 3). They were accompanied by *Acer negundo* L., *Aegopodium podagraria* L., *Prunus cerasifera* Ehrh., *Ranunculus ficaria* L., *Sambucus nigra* L., and others. Based on floristic studies by other authors (Trzcińska-Tacik 1979; Guzik 2006), this is the first documented spontaneous occurrence of *B. aquifolium* in Kraków. It is difficult to definitively confirm that *B. aquifolium* was once cultivated in this location, even though not all individuals appear to be remnants of cultivation. There are still many allotment gardens in the vicinity, where it is grown. Therefore, it is likely that it was introduced to this site via illegal dumping of garden waste. It is also possible that it was spread by birds feeding on its fleshy fruits, thereby dispersing its seeds via endozoochory. Such mechanisms of introduction and spread for *B. aquifolium* have already been suggested in the literature (Ross et al. 2008; Adriaens et al. 2019). Currently, *B. aquifolium* should be classified as a casual alien species in the local flora; however, its establishment and further spread are very likely.

Artur Pliszko & Grzegorz Pacyna (report 257)

Poland

257. *Viburnum lantana* L.: southern Poland, Lesser Poland Province, Kraków, roadside slope, three individuals, 223 m, 50°04.690'N 20°03.647'E, 25. 04. 2026, A. Pliszko & G. Pacyna, Fig. 4.

Viburnum lantana L. is a deciduous shrub, classified in the families Caprifoliaceae, Adoxaceae, or Viburnaceae, depending on taxonomic treatment (Kollmann & Grubb

2002; POWO 2026b). It is native to western, northern (United Kingdom), central, and southern Europe, northwestern Africa, and southwestern Asia. It was introduced as an ornamental or medicinal plant to other parts of Europe, northern Asia (Western Siberia), North America, and New Zealand (Kollmann & Grubb 2002; Randall 2017). It has been confirmed as a naturalized species in the United States, Canada, Russia, Ireland, Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania (Kollmann & Grubb 2002; Randall 2017). Moreover, it is considered invasive in European Russia (Borissova 2006) and potentially invasive in the United States (Herron et al. 2007). *V. lantana* reproduces generatively by seeds and vegetatively by root suckers (Kollmann & Grubb 2002). The seeds are easily dispersed by frugivorous birds, which facilitates its escape from cultivation (Kollmann & Grubb 2002; Dobravolskaitė & Gudžinskas 2011; Czarnecka et al. 2012).

Fig. 3 *Mahonia aquifolium* in Kraków, southern Poland: (A) – upper part of the shoot with inflorescences; (B) – general habitus of the species in ruderal thickets. Photographed by A. Pliszko.

Within its native range in Europe, *V. lantana* is usually found in shrublands and on forest edges, as well as on roadsides and hedges, and less frequently in forest gaps, primarily in well-drained, neutral to alkaline soils. It prefers suboceanic to subcontinental climate and thermal requirements in summer limit its spread northwards (Kollmann & Grubb 2002; InfoFlora 2026). The seedlings of *V. lantana* are shade-tolerant but in later stages it is more light-demanding (Kollmann 1997).

According to Mirek et al. (2020), *V. lantana* has an uncertain status in Poland. It has been speculated that it may be native, e.g. to the Polish part of the Eastern Sudetes. However, after years of cultivation, it is difficult to clearly distinguish anthropogenic from presumed natural sites of this species (Seneta & Dolatowski 2025). Contrastingly, some researchers (Tokarska-Guzik et al. 2012; Danielewicz et al. 2020) treat *V. lantana* as an alien species throughout the country. *V. lantana* is cultivated in gardens, parks and cemeteries, from where it occasionally escapes

(Purcel 2009; Czarna 2016; Jackowiak et al. 2017; Seneta & Dolatowski 2025). Furthermore, it has become established in some regions of western and central Poland but is not considered invasive (Kosiński & Bednorz 2003; Tokarska-Guzik et al. 2012; Danielewicz et al. 2020; Seneta & Dolatowski 2025). It usually inhabits forest edges and mid-field woodlots (Purcel 2009; Danielewicz et al. 2020).

In April 2026, we discovered a new locality of *V. lantana* in southern Poland. We found three flowering individuals on a roadside slope along Solidarności Avenue, within a construction area near the S7 expressway in eastern Kraków. The site was dominated by ruderal plant species, including *Acer negundo* L., *Alliaria petiolata* (M. Bieb.) Cavara & Grande, *Chelidonium majus* L., *Erigeron annuus* (L.) Desf., *Galium aparine* L., *Lamium album* L., *Urtica dioica* L. and others (Fig. 4). This is the first record of *V. lantana* in Kraków (compared with results by Trzcińska-Tacik 1979 and Guzik 2006) and it should currently be treated as a casual alien species in the local flora. It was most likely introduced accidentally from urban green spaces during the construction of the S7 expressway (e.g. roots, branches, or seeds may have been carried with the soil or on machinery) or by birds from nearby allotment gardens. Further spread of *V. lantana* in Kraków is likely, so monitoring its population is important for protecting native biodiversity.

Fig. 4 *Viburnum lantana* in Kraków, southern Poland: (A) – shoot with inflorescence; (B) – shrub growing on a roadside slope. Photographed by A. Pliszko.

Bohumil Trávníček & Matej Dudáš (reports 258-260)

Slovakia

258. *Taraxacum croceiflorum* Dahlst.: Západné Beskydy hill area, Čadca, settlement Križkovci, meadows and roadsides in northern part of the settlement, ca 550 m, 49°28'50.7"N 18°41'20.8"E, 6578a, 14. 5. 2004, B. Trávníček & R. J. Vašut, OL. – the Slanské vrchy Mts, Herľany, meadow near spring Kyslá voda, 388 m, 48°48'5.764"N

21°28'46.007"E, 7194d, 1. 5. 2026, B. Trávníček & M. Dudáš, KO 38971, iNat ID 366428489, Fig. 5.

Taraxacum croceiflorum, an apomictic species belonging to *Taraxacum* sect. *Taraxacum* Kirschner, Øllgaard et Štěpánek, is distributed in northwestern and northern Europe, in Central Europe it reaches southern limit of the species area. It prefers oceanic climate and its occurrence in Slovakia was recorded in mesophilic and slightly wet meadows. Morphologically it is similar to *Taraxacum lacerifolium* G. E. Haglund. During intensive field research in Slovakia focused on the genus *Taraxacum*, two localities of this previously not reported species were found, one in northwestern (near Čadca) and one in eastern (Herľany) part of the country. This is the first records for the flora of Slovakia.

Fig. 5 *Taraxacum croceiflorum*, herbarium specimen from Herľany, E Slovakia (KO 38971).

259. *Taraxacum lippertianum* Sahlin: Nízke Beskydy hill area, Bardejovské kúpele, sidewalk on south margin of main parking lot, ca 317 m, 49°19'33.006"N 21°16'37.575"E, 6693d, 1. 5. 2026, B. Trávníček & M. Dudáš, KO 38970, iNat ID 364045386, Fig. 6.

Taraxacum lippertianum, an apomictic species belonging to *Taraxacum* sect. *Taraxacum*, is central European species with disjunctive area occupying Germany (Bavaria), Denmark and the Czech Republic. Its taxonomy is not satisfactorily resolved; the species is often synonymized with *T. lojoëns* H. Lindb. fil., *T. debrayi* Hagendijk, Soest et Zevenbergen, *T. ampelophytum* Sahlin a *T. matricicum* Sahlin. The record from northeastern Slovakia is the first one for the flora of Slovakia. Only a single plant was found on sidewalk on south margin of the main parking lot in eastern part of Bardejovské kúpele spa area. Despite intensive inspection of the area, no further individuals were found, and the site will need to be monitored further in future to capture the variability of the species.

Fig. 6 *Taraxacum lippertianum*, herbarium specimen from Bardejovské kúpele, E Slovakia (KO 38970).

260. *Taraxacum expallidiforme* Dahlst.: the Východoslovenská nížina lowland, distr. Trebišov, Zemplín, grassy area under poplar trees on bank at confluence of rivers Latorica and Ondava, several plants, 100 m, 48°27'16.069"N 21°49'7.952"E, 7596b, 25. 4. 2026, M. Dudáš, KO 38954, 38955, iNat ID 367486190. – the Košická kotlina Basin, Košice, Sever, Botanická záhrada of Pavol J. Šafárik University, fork in the road leading from greenhouses towards garages, near building nearby hotbeds, tens plants, 232 m, 48°44'3.201"N 21°14'13.214"E, 7293c, 30. 4. 2026, B. Trávníček & M. Dudáš, KO 38958, 38959, iNat IDs 364054779, 364054780, 364054773. – the Nízke Beskydy hill area, Humenné, Park Mieru, between Podvihorlatské múzeum and

Amfiteáter, infrequent, 165 m, 48°56'20.343"N 21°54'33.409"E, 7097c, B. Trávníček & M. Dudáš, KO 38956, 38957, iNat ID 364057952, Fig. 7.

Taraxacum expallidiforme, an apomictic species belonging to *Taraxacum* sect. *Taraxacum*, is distributed from northwestern to northern and central part of Europe from British Isles, Iceland and France to Netherland, Denmark, Germany, the Scandinavian peninsula, Latvia, Poland and the Czech Republic. Previously not reported Slovak localities probably form the southern limit of the species area and can also be expected in Hungary. The species was found in shaded lawns in city parks and in a grassy area on a bank of the river in floodplain area.

Fig. 7 *Taraxacum expallidiforme*, herbarium specimen from Humenné, E Slovakia (KO 38956).

Radim J. Vašut (reports 261-263)

Czechia

261. *Sorbus hybrida* L.: Czechia, eastern Moravia, distr. Vsetín, ORP Rožnov p. Radh., Hutisko-Solanec – Solanec, southern bushy border of montane meadow near the cottage Solanec #191, approx. 400 m NNE of the top of the Račkov Mt. (853 m), 840 m, 49.3867697N 18.2271622E, 01. 10. 2022, R. J. Vašut, OL 52968; 19.08.2023, R. J. Vašut, OL 50045. – Hutisko-Solanec – Solanec, eastern bushy border of montane meadow near the cottage Solanec #191, approx. 500 m NNE (38°) of the top of the Račkov Mt. (853 m), 840 m, 49.3874000N 18.2281400E, 19. 08. 2023, R. J. Vašut, OL 50046, iNat ID 366797241, 366800287, Fig. 8.

Sorbus hybrida (recently known as *Hedlundia hybrida* (L.) Sennikov & Kurtto; e.g. WFO (wfo-0001428017), or POWO (urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:77164914-1) is an apomictic species naturally occurring in Northern Europe and naturalised in Italy (Sennikov & Kurtto 2017). It is a popular ornamental tree in temperate Europe, although it is cultivated less frequently than some other *Sorbus* s.l. species.

Here, we report the repeated causal occurrence of seedlings originating from a cultivated tree. Since their first detection on 7 May 2018, several tens of seedlings have been observed at the site, with some individuals already reaching a height of several metres. This indicates that the offspring plant can survive for at least several years at this site (last observation on 7 Dec 2025). Found in shrub-dominated ecotonal vegetation at the margin of a meadow, extending into the edge of a beech forest. The mother plant of spreading offspring is a cultivated tree grafted onto *Sorbus aucuparia*. Flow-cytometric seed screening (FCSS; Matzk et al. 2000) confirmed pseudogamous seed formation, with a 2n embryo and 6n endosperm.

Fig. 8 Young plants of *Sorbus hybrida* in the Vsetínské vrchy hills near Hutisko-Solanec. Photo Radim J. Vašut, 19. 08. 2023.

262. *Styphnolobium japonicum* (L.) Schott: Czechia, central Moravia, distr. Olomouc, Olomouc – Černovír, in ruderal successional shrub vegetation between the cycle path and the railway, east of the settlement, ca. 215 m, 49.6212856N 17.2645500E, Radim J. Vašut, OL 52962; 26.10.2021 & 10.07.2023, Radim J. Vašut, notavit; 30.05.2026, Radim J. Vašut, OL 52967. iNat ID 366794805, Fig. 9.

Styphnolobium japonicum (traditionally known as *Sophora japonica*) is a popular ornamental tree in Europe. Its popularity has been increasing in recent decades due to climate change, as the species is considered a promising ornamental tree for overheated urban environments in Central Europe. The species has occasionally been reported as escaped from cultivation, although it is not considered an invasive alien species and apparently has a low rate of spread. Escaped or spontaneously occurring plants have been documented from Spain (Gassó et al. 2012), Italy (Galasso et al. 2018), Croatia (Hulina 2010), Hungary (Bartha 2001), and Ukraine (Burda & Koniakin 2019). However, the species has not yet been documented as an alien plant in Czechia (Danihelka et al. 2012; Pyšek et al. 2022).

The species was first observed as an inconspicuous young tree approximately 2 m tall, with a slender stem, growing in ruderal shrub vegetation along a railway line. Upon revisiting the site, at least three well-developed multi-stemmed trees several metres tall were found, clearly overtopping the surrounding scrub vegetation. The species grows together with *Acer platanoides*, *A. pseudoplatanus*, *A. negundo*, *Robinia pseudoacacia*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Prunus padus*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Euonymus europaeus*, *Cornus sanguinea* and *Rubus caesius*. The occurrence is apparently casual, and the species seems to persist only locally without evidence of further spread.

263. *Primula* × *digenea* A.Kern.: Czechia, eastern Moravia, distr. Vsetín, ORP Rožnov p. Radh., Hutisko-Solanec – Hutisko, grassland in orchard in private garden in centre of village, approx. 0.2 km south-west (237°) of the church (sv. Josef), ca. 500 m, 49.4309828N 18.2183892E (± 15 m), 09.05.2021, R. J. Vašut, OL 52900, iNat ID 366801216, Fig. 10.

Primula vulgaris, *Primula veris*, and *Primula elatior* are widespread species in Europe, although sympatric populations involving *P. vulgaris* and either of the latter two species are relatively rare. *Primula vulgaris* is known to hybridise with both *P. veris* and *P. elatior*. Hybridisation between *P. vulgaris* and *P. elatior* was documented in Great Britain (Valentine 1952) and more recently confirmed using molecular markers in Denmark (Tendal et al. 2018). Regionally, hybrids involving *P. vulgaris* may form hybrid populations (e.g. Bauer & Cservenka 2002; Kalman et al. 2004). However, no hybrids involving *P. vulgaris* have yet been documented from Czechia (Danihelka et al. 2012).

The occurrence reported here represents a unique and isolated case. *Primula vulgaris* is cultivated as an ornamental plant in the garden, whereas *P. elatior* occurs naturally in the surrounding grasslands and adjacent gardens. The hybrid individual was observed for three years but has since disappeared from the site. No additional

hybrid plants have been recorded, suggesting that hybrid formation is apparently very rare under local conditions.

Fig. 9 Naturalized occurrence of *Styphnolobium japonicum* in ruderal scrub vegetation in Olomouc-Černovír. Photo by Radim J. Vašut, 30 May 2026.

Fig. 10 Habitus of hybrid primrose *P. × digenea* found in private garden in Hutisko-Solanec. Photo Radim J. Vašut, 09. 05. 2021. Half of this plant is deposited as herbarium specimen OL 52900.

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